

School Education: The Paradox; Higher Education: More Paradox

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School Education: The Paradox

Education that until a few centuries ago used to be the privilege of a few rich people has become the demand of the masses. The question is no longer whether we should have excellence or equity in education. It will have to be excellence with equity. After food and shelter, education has emerged as the most important priority of the people in today's world because it is considered the key to economic prosperity for an individual as well as that of a nation. If Tsar Nicholas II wanted a system of education where every person should remain happy with his position and will not try to rise further, the political bosses in the Soviet Union wanted education to create good communists. The Soviet experiment has two lessons for us. First, a person of any background can be educated. (The first generation of Soviet scientists, engineers, economists, philosophers etc. had entirely come from working class and poor farmer parents). Second, education, whatever may be its aim, makes a person think and he becomes capable of questioning the usefulness, or otherwise, of the most established norms of a society. He can change the most entrenched system, as proved by the extinction of Soviet Union.

There is enough empirical evidence to show that education improves the overall quality of life. Even basic literacy (ability to read, write and perform simple arithmetic) improves one's earning power. This was not realized in the first fifteen years of independence when vocational training was

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tried to be imparted even before literacy. Education enables a person to participate more effectively in the democratic process as it gives him a voice. He/she becomes better enabled to tackle health problem and also to fight social evils. Women's education is important in empowering women in taking decisions within and outside family. It hardly needs convincing that education brings social benefit and we have seen a huge expansion of elementary education and also the Right to Education Act. India's education budget stands at a reasonable 3.78 percent of GDP (in 2008-09). According to the latest report (2013), there are 23 crore students in 1.3 million schools throughout India, but adult literacy (age 15 and above) still languished at 74 percent (female 65.5%) according to 2011 census. The same for China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, Thailand and Vietnam is between 91 and 95 percent. Some of these nations got their independence after India. Among school goers (age group 8-11 years) in India, only 50 in every hundred can read a simple paragraph, 43 can subtract two-digit number and 64 can write a simple sentence with two or lesser number of errors. Do not blame the government schools only as the corresponding figures in the hallowed private schools are also quite unsatisfactory at 69, 64 and 79 respectively.

Talking of higher education, according to one of India's most respected entrepreneurs, forty percent of the engineering graduates are unemployable. At the same time, we find that some of the Indian engineering and science graduates are the most sought after by the Industry and Universities of the developed countries. In fact, during the last Presidential election in the USA, there was a hue and cry in American media that highly skilled Indian are snatching jobs from the locals, even suggesting changes in the US education system to face the challenge. Here lies the paradox of our education system. Obviously, high quality higher education can be sustained only on the back of a good primary and secondary education. We shall talk about higher education later. Let us examine what ails elementary education in India.

What are the causes of poor learning and performance of students in our schools and what are the remedies? One can go on enumerating the causes such as poor infrastructure, poor nutrition of the children, poor quality and

indifference of teachers, high student to teacher ratio, poor salary of teachers etc. Some people even advocate that government should hand over the entire education sector to private players. But it is also true that the excellent quality of students do come out in a small percent (but not an insignificant number in the absolute count) from the same schools, both government and private. Let us examine some of the causes.

There is little dispute about the poor quality of infrastructure in the government managed schools although a survey in 2006 in 200 randomly selected schools in seven of the most backward states has revealed appreciable improvement in this front. Seventy three percent of these schools had a minimum two durable rooms (as compared to 26 percent in 1996), 60 percent had toilets, more than 70 percent had drinking water, all pupils were provided with free textbooks, cooked midday meals were provided in 86 percent of these schools. This, of course, is a far cry from what it should be, but a significant improvement no doubt. So lack of infrastructure cannot be entirely blamed for the down trend in pupil's achievement. A severe deficiency was attendance by the students as well as by the teachers. Nearly one-thirds of the students were found absent on any given day and so were a number of teachers. Late arrival and early leaving was found to be the norm. About 12 percent schools functioned with one teacher in the payroll and his absence meant no class. There are cases of single-teacher schools where the teacher leases out part of his job to some unemployed educated youth by sharing a fraction of his pay. Such acts of omission and commission go unpunished as there is hardly any supervision. To add to this, many schools functioned without a permanent Head Master who could impose some discipline on the erring teachers.

A generally touted theory for poor performance of our schools is the poor salary of the teacher. It is true that teachers' salary used to be very low. In the early fifties when this author was student in a famous school of lower Assam, a graduate mathematics teacher was paid a paltry sum of Rs. 60 a month. Pay of the government school teachers has significantly risen after several pay commissions that forced the private schools also to increase the salary. Indian teachers are definitely at an advantage over their counterparts in other developing countries. If in Indonesia a teacher's pay is

only 0.5 times its GDP (in Japan it is 1.5 times), in Uttar Pradesh (the most educationally backward state in India), it was 6.4 times the GDP in 2006 and it was 5.9 times of India's GDP in the state of Bihar in 2012. In fact, this large increase in salary of the teacher has created a new affluent class amidst the poverty-stricken Indian villagers. In our school days, all teachers used to put their own children in the same school in which they taught. Today, most rural teachers of government schools send their children to private schools. This too is a reason for their not taking sufficient interest in teaching. In the Indian system, once a teacher (or for that matter, any govt. employee) is appointed, he cannot be removed. Because of the high salary, government is unable to appoint the required number of teachers within the budgetary provision making the class size unmanageable. Contract teachers are often appointed at a much lower salary. Because of the permanent threat to their jobs, there is reason to believe that they do a more sincere job than the regular teachers. Even when a teacher is active, he pays more attention to the better achievers among the students depriving the weaker students who really need his attention more urgently.

Lack of evaluation of the learners' achievement is another lacuna in our schools. The oppressive annual examination of the earlier years that encouraged rote learning has been abolished and pupil are automatically promoted up to Class 8. Although there is provision for continuous assessment and evaluation, this is hardly done with any seriousness. The teacher knows that she will have to promote the student irrespective his/her performance and does not feel any urge to evaluate. The reason why most adults are educated up to Class 8 is this system of automatic promotion. It is most important that we devise a method of evaluation that is authentic without being oppressive.

Is Privatisation a Solution?

Some people feel that the government should hand over school education to private players who can handle it much better. Past experience on this points the other way. Modern school education that started in Europe in the early nineteenth century and in Japan in mid-nineteenth century were both at the initiative of the State. The tremendous educational achievements of the ex-communist countries were entirely at the initiative of the State. The

task is too enormous for private parties to handle, although private initiatives are welcome and will be always there both by the Missionaries as well as by profit-making organisations. Moreover, lack of competition in the rural areas will lead to unfair practice that will be difficult to control. Going by the student achievement, private schools are not very much better than the state run schools, particularly the better run Kendriya Vidyalayas. In fact, in the CBSE conducted board examinations, the performance by the latter is better than the private school students taking the same examination.

The State cannot wash off its hand from school education as it is her responsibility to give better life to its citizens. What is needed is to lay down proper policy and implement it with all checks and balances for which close scrutiny of the schools is very important. Our policy makers should give serious thought to the problems of schools some of which has been raised here.

Higher Education: More Paradox

Since antiquity, India had a tradition of higher education restricted to a small group of the upper caste in the so-called *Gurukul* system. It flourished and then was enlarged in the middle age, and Nalanda became the centre of learning where scholars from all over the world came to study many subjects besides the Buddhist religion. When the first University was established in Europe in 1088 AD, Nalanda was six hundred years old. It was severely damaged by Bakhtiar Khilji and could never fully recover from the savagery of that assault and slowly lost its glory. There were several other less known but important centres of learning. However, the modern schools of higher education began in India when the British rulers started in 1857 Universities of Calcutta, Bombay and Madras. At the time of independence, there were 21 Universities in India. At present, India boasts of 544 Universities – 261 State, 42 Central, 73 Private, 130 Deemed University besides 79 autonomous centrally funded institutions. This large growth notwithstanding, academic achievement of Indian students and teachers remains miserably poor. No Indian University finds a place among the top two hundred in the world although a few from Japan, China, Hong Kong and Singapore find place below the top twenty. (A few of the Indian Institutes of Technology come close to the top 200; they miss the rank because

of the limited number of disciplines taught by them and lower student enrollment). The paradox is that some of our graduates do extremely well after they join some of the best Universities in the United States. Many top Universities in the USA seek the bright Indian graduates. The explanation is that a small percent of Indian students (but not a small number) get excellent education and training in a few good Institutions that exist in India. It is a fact that the IITs and IIMs offer excellent education by any standard. Not all the teachers even in these Institutes can be considered excellent. The statement by the minister Jayram Ramesh (a IIT Bombay alumnus) that the IITs do well because of the quality of the students and not teachers may have some truth, notwithstanding his penchant for controversy. But even the best have not done much in terms of path-breaking original work. Our best is very good at problem solving, but is not the same when it comes to formulating original problems and asking fundamental questions. However, it is a fact that Indian institutes of higher learning are extremely diverse in standard. There are some excellent institutes in India and selected departments of some Universities are very good. But the performance of the vast majority of the Universities is alarming. What is the reason of this poor state of higher education in India?

There are several reasons. The preparation of the students before they enter college is one major hindrance to higher education. In a previous article, we have discussed the state of education in our schools. As a result, college syllabus repeats almost the entire syllabus of the +2 stage. Similarly, the Masters Degree programme repeats the degree syllabus to begin with. Not that the students improve as a result of this repetition, but valuable time is lost. By the time they reach college, students are already used to rote learning and even good teachers do not find it easy to make them think independently. Obtaining good grade has become easy because of the so-called continuous evaluation and “objective” questions. One may pass with a first class with little understanding of the subject. Such graduates then join the pool of incompetent teachers.

Traditionally, teachers were poorly paid. Nowadays, a teacher generally joins a University or College at the average age of about thirty years. This author started his career in a IIT at a take-home salary of Rs. 450. At such a low salary even in 1967, it was very difficult to balance the family budget

particularly in the Indian society where the old parents remain dependents. Financial worry makes it difficult for a young faculty to concentrate at his job. This has been corrected to some extent only before the turn of the century and improved further in the year 2006. But this sudden windfall brought a large number of undesirable persons in the fold of the teachers. Many of those who were already in the system when the change happened were deeply entrenched in secondary work. As a result, improvement of the pay package failed to produce the desired result.

The method of selection of the College and University teacher is pathetic. The fraud on the system generally begins at the level of scrutiny of application at which stage applicants not belonging to the region where the University is located are systematically removed. This is considered a patriotic duty. There is a system in which points are allotted for the class secured in the examinations, higher degree (MPhil or PhD), years of experience, performance in the interview etc., but ability of the candidate to teach is not examined at any stage. One or two experts in the subject concerned are included in the Committee. Experts are picked up by the Vice-Chancellor from a list provided by the Head of the concerned department who generally prepare the list not necessarily on the basis of competence of the expert but on personal relation with himself and his pliability. In my long experience in these committees all over India, I have seen the same pattern being repeated again and again. Even the Vice-Chancellors are not selected on merit and that becomes apparent from the comment of none less than the Prime Minister of India who said, *“I am concerned that in many states university appointments, including that of Vice-Chancellors, have been politicised and have become subject to caste and communal considerations, there are complaints of favouritism and corruption”*.

The system of reward of the University teachers is also faulty. After a fixed number of years, a teacher (Assistant or Associate Professor) becomes eligible for selection to the next higher position until he becomes a Professor. He is now asked how many papers has he published, how many PhD students has he guided and how many conferences has he attended. No one asks how well did he teach, what do the students think of him. In other words, his ability to teach and teach well is of no consequence. There is no way of ascertaining this as most Colleges and Universities do not have a

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system of course evaluation by the students, no peer review is done either. Given the situation, most teachers do not take teaching seriously. In India, there is nothing like tenure appointment. Once appointed, a teacher cannot be removed and because of the limited avenue of reaching the next higher stage of his career, normally he takes it easy and diverts his attention to other activities. Problem also arises because of the high student to teacher ratio in the colleges that makes individualized attention difficult. Bodies like Education Commission, Knowledge Commission etc. operate from high horses separated from reality and statements like “teachers are facilitators only” are often misunderstood.

If teaching is of poor standard, research is even poorer. Most Universities are poorly equipped both in terms of library and laboratory to carry out any outstanding research and college teachers are not even expected to do any. Although there are centralized facilities located in some campuses, the clumsy procedure and tendency to monopolize them by a few makes it difficult for majority to access these. Indians are poor collaborators and collaborative research is almost unknown. Universities and colleges are periodically assessed by NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council) but the credibility of NAAC is doubtful.

Government is trying to expand the higher education sector too rapidly and already 15 percent of the youth in the relevant age group are enrolled and the target is 20 percent by 2020. If attention is not paid to the fault lines, we shall be soon producing a mass of illiterate graduates in the country.